

Yield and quality characteristics of improved basmati donors. Hyderabad, India, 1988.

Character	Pusa 367-152 (Pusa 167-2/Type 3)	Pusa 615-140-10-10 (IET10364) (Pusa 167/Karnal Local)	Pusa 751-1-2 (Pusa 367-4-2-2/Type 3)	Traditional local varieties		
				Karnal Local	Basmati 370	Type 3
Plant height (cm)	80-85	90-95	90-100	135-150	135-150	135-150
Growth duration (d)	145-150	135-140	140-145	145-150	135-140	135-140
Yield (t/ha)	3.0-4.0	4.0-5.0	2.5-3.0	2.0-2.5	2.0-3.0	2.0-3.0
Test grain weight (g)	25.92	22.80	27.54	22.00	20.53	18.60
Length of milled rice (mm)	7.63	6.98	8.37	7.35	6.87	6.71
Breadth of milled rice (mm)	2.00	1.70	1.90	1.78	1.89	1.84
L:B ratio	3.81	4.11	4.40	4.13	3.63	3.64
Length of kernel after cooking (mm)	16.20	14.70	18.37	13.89	13.64	13.22
Elongation ratio	2.12	2.01	2.19	1.89	1.98	1.97
Alkali spreading value	4	4	4	4	4	4
Amylose (%)	24.00	28.00	24.50	25.50	22.00	22.50
Presence of aroma ^a	M.S.	S	S.S.	S	S	S

^a M.S. = mildly scented, S = scented, S.S. = strongly scented.

and low grain number. In spite of poor yield, their unique cooking quality fetches the highest premium in the national and international markets.

Karnal Local, Basmati 370, and Type 3 are the most widely cultivated varieties. However, Karnal Local's higher kernel length and higher length:breadth ratio give it preference in the market.

After two decades of intensive

convergent breeding with rigorous screening and selection, IARI has developed three promising basmati lines: Pusa 367-152, Pusa 615-140-10-1, and Pusa 751-1-2 (see table). Pusa 367-152 has excellent plant type with stiff stem and dark green erect leaves. It has desirable cooking qualities; however, grain shattering, late maturity, and mild aroma are drawbacks. Pusa 615-140-10-1 has good plant type and all important

basmati components, but with relatively higher amylose content. Pusa 751-1-2 is much superior to traditional basmati in cooking quality and aroma but does not yield well because of low grain number and relatively moderate tillering.

Among them, Pusa 615-140-10-1 (IET10364) has been selected for farm trials. All three lines may be useful as donors in the basmati rice improvement program. □

Saleem and Satya released for Andhra Pradesh, India

Mohinikashikar, V. Hasan, R. V. Kumar, and N. V. Nanda, Agricultural Research Institute, Andhra Pradesh Agricultural University, Hyderabad 500030, A. P., India

Saleem and Satya were released for general cultivation in 1987 for Andhra Pradesh, particularly for Telangana region. Semidwarf Saleem, derived from GEB 24/Sigadis//IR8/RNR8102, has 135 d duration in monsoon. It will grow in winter with irrigation. From 1972 to 1982, it yielded 6.4 t/ha average in monsoon, 27% more than Jaya, Jagannath, and Prakash. In winter, it registered 7.5 t/ha, 10.8% more than Jaya and Sona. In farmers' fields over 7 districts, it outyielded Tella Hamsa and Mahsuri by 21%. It has long slender grains with length:breadth ratio 3.5.

Satya, from the cross Tella Hamsa/Rasi, has 120 d duration in monsoon and 130 d in winter and

tolerates cold in vegetative phase. It tolerates bacterial blight and sheath blight. It has white long slender grains. From 1980 to 1986, it produced 5.4 t/ha

in monsoon and 5.0 t/ha in winter, 14.3% more than Tella Hamsa in monsoon and 38.4% more than Tella Hamsa and IR50 in winter. □

Mutant glutinous rice variety Xiang-zao-nou 1

Wan Xianguo, Pang Boliang, and Zhu Xiaqi, Institute for Application of Atomic Energy, Hunan Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Changsha, Hunan, China

Xiang-zao-nou 1 is a new glutinous rice variety with good quality, high yields, and multiple resistance. It was developed by irradiating F₂ dry seeds of IR29/ Wen-Xwan-qing with 27.9 kR of ⁶⁰Co-gamma rays.

Xiang-zao-nou 1 has good plant type, desirable yielding components, and wide adaptability. It matures in 117 d in the early season in Hunan Province, China. Generally, it can yield 6.75 t/ha in the

early season or 6 t/ha in late season. It is highly resistant to bacterial blight and blast, and is very good in grain quality and glutinosity. This variety was grown on more than 220,000 ha 1983-87. □

P.837 — a promising new rice variety for Pondicherry, India

P. Narayanasamy, S. R. S. Rangasamy, R. S. Purushothaman, and B. Rajendran, Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Pondicherry, India

In Pondicherry region (11°45' - 12°15' N and 79°35' - 80°00' E), half the crop area is planted to rice Aug-Sep to Dec-